

EFFECT OF INGESTION OF GARCINIA KOLA SEED ON ERYTHROCYTES IN RABBITS

Unigwe, C.R. and Nwakpu, P.E.

Department of Animal Science, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki P. M. B 053.

ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to investigate the effect on RBC of ground untreated *Garcinia kola* seed in rabbits. Twenty four unsexed rabbits with average weight of 842.62+ 57.5g and aged between 42 and 49 days were randomly assigned to four treatments of T₁ (control, no bitter kola) T₂ (1g bitter kola/kg body weight), T₃ (2g bitter kola/kg body weight) and T₄(3g bitter kola/kg body weight) in a completely randomized design. Each of the treatments was replicated thrice with two rabbits per replicate. They were given graded levels of bitter kola treatments for four out of seven days weekly for 12 weeks excepting T₁. At the end of the experiment blood samples were collected and the red blood cell (RBC) concentration, packed cell volume (PCV) and haemoglobin concentration values were determined. The results showed that T₄ and T₃ were highly significant (P<0.01) in haemoglobin concentration. In the same vein T₄, T₃ and T₂ demonstrated highly significant difference (P<0.01) in RBC counts. However, there was no significant difference (P>0.05) in PCV among all the treatments. None of the values fell below the normal physiological range of the experimental animals. This shows that *Garcinia kola* which has flavonoids as its active constituent can enhance erythropoiesis and as well has no long term significant toxicological implication with respect to the above concentrations.

KEYWORDS: *Garcinia kola* , haemoglobin concentration, erythropoiesis, flavonoids, toxicological implication

INTRODUCTION

The tolerance of orthodox antibiotics in the recent time has posed more questions than answers (Hong-xi and Song, 2001). Antibiotic cross resistance manifests in humans after consuming meat from animals earlier placed on antibiotic chemotherapy in which the withdrawal period for such antibiotic had not been met before slaughter (Walton, 1996).

Garcinia kola seed known as bitter kola in Nigeria is commonly called “*Namiji goro*” in Hausa and “*Akilu*” in Igbo (Esomonu, *et al.*, 2005) is used in traditional medicine for various therapeutic purposes based on the pharmacological effects of the active components (flavonoid) in the seed and other parts of the plant (Braide and Vittrorio, 1989). *Garcinia kola* also serves as a guinea-worm remedy (Lewis, *et al.*, 1977), and employed in the treatment of diabetes (Tita, *et al.*, 2001). Wang, *et al.* (2000) also reported that flavonoid supplements are likely to be beneficial for long-term health since it acts as a potent antioxidant.

The seed has also been shown to have antibiotic property by Hong-xi and Song, (2001) and anti-inflammatory property (Braide, 1990) as well as antimicrobial activity (Madubuyi,1995). Bearing in mind that much work has not been done in *Garcinia kola*,I was moved to investigate its effect on erythrocytes of rabbits.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

EXPERIMENTAL ANIMALS AND MANAGEMENT

Twenty four rabbits with average weight of 842.62+57.5g and aged between 42 and 49 days were divided into four treatments of T₁ (control, no bitter kola), T₂ (1g bitter kola /kg body weight), T₃ (2g bitter kola/kg body weight), and T₄ (3g bitter kola/kg body weight). They were replicated into three with two rabbits each. The rabbits in T₂, T₃ and T₄ were given ground bitter kola seed as prescribed above every four out of seven days weekly for twelve weeks. The ground bitter kola was suspended in 30ml of water and served to them per day after water deprivation for about 2-3 hours. Within a spell of few to forty five minutes, they had consumed the whole treatment. Then commercial Guinea Feed with

TABLE 1.0: HAEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF RABBITS MEDICATED WITH GRADED LEVELS OF BITTER KOLA

Blood parameters	T ¹	T ²	T ³	T ⁴	SEM
Hgb (g/dl)	11.70 ^c	11.10 ^d	13.03 ^b	13.80 ^a	0.16
PCV(%)	41	41	42	44	0.65
RBC(/mm ³)	5.60x10 ^{6b}	6.93x10 ^{6a}	6.95x10 ^{6a}	7.10x10 ^{6a}	0.13
WBC (/L)	6.20X10 ⁹	6.20X10 ⁹	6.0X10 ⁹	6.10X10 ⁹	0.09

abc:rows with different superscripts on the same line are statistically different(P<0.05).

crude protein of 14.5% and metabolisable energy of 2300 kcal/kg was measured and served them. Also clean drinking water (tap) was given *ad-libitum*.

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

At the end of the experiment occult blood was collected via the ear vein from each treatment. The blood was used to determine red blood cell (RBC) count, packed cell volume (PCV), and haemoglobin (Hgb) concentration in the laboratory based on the method described by Schalm, *et al*, (1975).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The average values of the indices were determined and the standard errors of mean calculated. Values got were compared with those of control and where differences existed in means, it was separated using Fisher's Least Square Difference (F-LSD). These were used to compute the levels of significance at P<0.05 and P<0.01.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HAEMATOLOGICAL PARAMETERS

Table 1 shows that there was a gradual increase in haemoglobin as the bitter kola levels increased from T₂ (11.1g/dl) to T₃ (13.03g/dl) and T₄ (13.8g/dl) while rabbit in T₁ has 11.7g/dl of haemoglobin. Rabbits on T₃ and T₄ showed highly significant difference (P<0.01) in treatment effect when compared with those on T₂ and T₁. There was no significant difference (P>0.05) when T₃ and T₄ were compared. Also the same significance (P>0.05) existed when T₁ and T₂ were compared.

The PCV showed no significant difference (P>0.05) due to the treatments when rabbits on T₁(41%), T₂(41%), T₃(42%) and T₄(44%) were compared. Although this shows a progressive increase in PCV as the treatment increased in concentration. The RBC counts showed a highly significant difference (P<0.01) in treatment effects of bitter kola when rabbits on T₂ (6.93x10⁶RBC/mm³) T₃ (6.95X10⁶RBC/mm²), and T₄ (7.10X10⁶RBC/mm³) were compared with T₁(5.6X10⁶RBC/mm³). However, there was no significant differences (P>0.05) when treatment effects of bitter kola on RBC were compared among T₂, T₃ and T₄. All fell within the normal physiological range of rabbits as established by Mitruka and Rawnsely,(1977) and Ross *et al*, (1978).

The steady rise in the values of PCV, RBC and Hgb concentration as the bitter kola seed concentration increased might be due to the antioxidant activity of flavonoid (Bravo,1998, and Wang, *et al*, 2000) which was present in the blood due to *Garcinia kola* seed intake thereby elevating the total antioxidant capacity of the blood. The gradual steady rise in RBC count could also be as a result of increasing

freedom from disease since Brown and Clime, (1991), opined that increased RBC values are associated with high quality protein and with disease free animals.

The higher value obtained in haemoglobin concentration in T₁ (11.7g/dl) compared to T₂ (11.1g/dl) could either be ascribed to idiosyncrasy or due to complexes which flavonoid forms with reactive metals such as iron, zinc and copper thereby reducing the rabbits' nutrient absorption (Siegenberg, *et al.*, 1991). This happened since iron is bound in the complex which is a major component of haemoglobin. The same explanation goes for the similarity in PCV values of T₁ and T₂ since haemoglobin has a direct relationship with PCV. The highly significant difference (P<0.01) in RBC counts obtained from rabbits on graded bitter kola treatment could probably be that there was compensation when ageing RBCs were destroyed leading to release of some iron which were in turn salvaged and transported to the erythroid cells of the bone marrow for new haemoglobin and RBC syntheses (Conley, 1974).

Though there were varieties in haematological values, none fell below the normal physiological range of the experimental animals. This agrees with the work of Kou, (1997) who found no significant side effects evidenced from regular consumption of polyphenol or flavonoid containing dietary supplements. In conclusion, the constituent of *Garcinia kola* seed has been shown to exert no long-term significant toxicological tendency to erythrocytes rather it showed a marked tendency to increase the erythrocyte number. This is in tandem with the work of Esomonu, *et al.* (2005) who recorded increased RBC values in Wistar rats medicated with ethanol extract of *Garcinia kola* seed.

REFERENCES

- Braide, V.D. and Vittrotio, G. (1989). Histological Alterations by a Diet containing seeds of *Garcinia kola*: Effect on liver, kidney and intestine in the rat. In: *Gedenbaurs Morphol. Jahrb, Leipig*. 13341(5): 95-101.
- Braide, V.D.(1990). Pharmacological Effects of Chronic Ingestion of *Garcinia kola* Seeds in the Rats. *Phytotherapy Res.* (4):39-41.
- Bravo, L. (1998). Polyphenols: Chemistry, dietary source, metabolism and nutritional significances. *Nutr. Rev.* 56 (11): 317-333.
- Brown, J.A. and Clime, T.R. (1991).Comparative Haematology of Rabbit on Forage and Graded Concentrates. *J. Anim. Sci.* 35:211-218.
- Conley, C.L., (1974). The Blood: In Medical Physiology. Ed., Vernon, B.M. Volume 11. pp 1027-1057.
- Esomonu. U.G, El-aalu, A.B., Anuka, J.A., Ndodo, N.D., Salim, M.A., and Atiku, M.K. (2005): Effect of Ingestion of Ethanol Extract of *Garcinia kola* Seed on Erythrocytes in Wistar Rats. *J of physiological Sciences* 20 (1 and 2): 30-32.
- Hong-xi and Song, F.L. (2001). Activity of Plant Flavonoids Against Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria. *Phytother. Res.* 15:39-43.
- Kou, S.M. (1997). Dietary flavonoid and cancer prevention evidence and potential mechanism. *Crit Rev. oncology.* 8(1):47-9.
- Lewis, W.H.(1977). Medic Botany:Plants Effecting Mainsheath. New York:*John Wiley-int. pub.* Pp: 231- 232.
- Madubuyi, I.I (1995).Antimicrobial activities of the constituents of *Garcinia kola* seeds. *Int. J. Pharamacog.* 333:232-237.

Mitruka, B.M. and Rawnsley, H.M.(1977).Clinical, Biochemical and Haematological Reference Value in Normal Experimental Animals. Mason Publishing Company, New York; pp 35-50.

Ross, J.D., Christie, G., Holiday, W.G. and Jones, R.M. (1978). Haematological indices in chicken on range management. *Vet record*, 102:29-31.

Schalm, O.W., Jari, N.C. and Carroll, E. J. (1975). Veterinary Haematology. 3rd ed. Lea and Febiger, London, pp 385- 390.

Siegenberg, D., Baynes, R.D., Bothwell, T.H., Macferleane, B.J., Lamparelli, R.D., Car, N.G., Macphail, P., Schmidt, U., Tal, A., and Mayet, F. (1991). Ascorbic acid and the dose-dependent inhibitory effects of polyphenols and phytates on non haeme-iron absorption. *Am..J. Clin. Nutr.* 53(2) 537-41.

Tita, R.K., Odeigah, P.G.C., Agom, P.U. and Bassey, E. (2001). Some properties of medicinal plants used by the Igbo, of Nigeria.In Traits, Tracts and Traces. (Germany). Edited by Wolfgang Kreis pp 209-210.

Walton, J.R (1996). Benefits of Antibiotics in Animal Feed. The University of Liverpool, Veterinary Teaching Hospital, Leahurst, South Wirral, L647TE.UK.

Wang, J.F., Schramm, D.D., Holt, R.R., Ensunsa, J.L., Fraga, C.G., Schemitz, H.H., and Keen, C.L. (2000). A dose- response effect from chocolate consumption on plasma epicatechin and oxidative damage. *J. Nutr.* 130 (8 suppl.): 21155-95.

Received for Publication: 03/07/2008

Accepted for Publication: 25/08/2008

Corresponding Author:

Unigwe, C.R.

Department of Animal Science, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki P. M. B 053.